

Mono- and bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives with alkyl xanthates

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Abstract : Hafnium(IV) alkyl xanthates of the types $\text{Cp}_2\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$, where $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$ and $n\text{-C}_5\text{H}_{11}$, have been prepared by the reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride with potassium alkyl xanthates in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran. Conductance and infrared studies suggest that these complexes are non-electrolytes in which all of the xanthate ligands are bidentate. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of these complexes indicate that there is rapid rotation of the cyclopentadienyl ring about the metal-ring axis and for the $\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ complexes, non-equivalence of the alkyl xanthate ligands was observed.

Keywords : Hafnium(IV), xanthate, organohafnium compounds.

Though the chemistry of organohafnium(IV) derivatives with oxygen nitrogen centred ligands is well studied, only few papers have appeared on sulphur donor ligands^{1,2}. These include hafnocene(IV) thiolates, polychalcogenides and dithiocarbamate derivatives¹. Perhaps the most important application of these complexes is in a variety of asymmetric catalytic and stoichiometric reactions¹⁻⁸. In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of hafnium(IV) derivatives with alkyl xanthate viz. ethyl xanthate ($\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5$), propyl xanthate ($\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7$), butyl xanthate ($\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9$) and amyl xanthate ($\text{S}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11}$). The bidentate xanthate ligand by virtue of its low charge and relative small bite ($\sim 3 \text{ \AA}$) is particularly well suited for stabilisation of higher coordination states of metals⁹.

Results and discussion

A systematic study of the reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride with potassium salt of alkyl xanthates in 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 molar ratios respectively in dry tetrahydrofuran yielded the complexes of the type $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})\text{Cl}$ and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ according to the following equations :

where, $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, C_2H_7 , C_4H_9 and C_5H_{11} .

The method used for the preparation and isolation of these compounds give materials of good purity as supported by their analysis (Table 1) and TLC. All these complexes are brown in colour. Complexes of the $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ type are soluble in chloroform, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide and nitrobenzene whereas complexes of the $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3]$ are soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide and nitrobenzene. Conductance measurements in nitrobenzene reveal that they are essentially non-electrolytes. Magnetic susceptibility values at room temperature show their diamagnetic nature. Osmometric molecular weight determinations show the $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})$ derivatives to be dimeric and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ as monomeric, indicating the possibility of chlorine to be involved in the molecular association. The presence of electronegative chlorine atom in $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})$ derivatives tends to increase the electropositive character of hafnium and, consequently, its electron acceptor tendency increases and thus, probably causing intermolecular association. The $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ derivatives, in which one chloride ion is replaced by a xanthate group, are expected to possess comparatively less electropositive hafnium, thereby resulting in a decrease in their molecular association tendency.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of all these complexes show a single band in the $22200\text{--}23000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

Table 1. Characterization data for the mono- and bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes

Reactants (g, molar ratio)	Reflux time (h)	Product, colour (yield %)	Empirical formula (formula weight)	Decom. temp. (°C)	Found (Calcd.) %				
					C	H	S	Cl	Hf
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5$ (1.9 + 0.80, 1 : 1)	25	$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)$ Light brown (78)	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{OS}_2\text{HfCl}$ (465.33)	230	33.2 (33.5)	3.0 (3.2)	13.4 (13.8)	7.5 (7.6)	38.1 (38.3)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5$ (1.9 + 2.4, 1 : 3)	40	$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ Brown (70)	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{S}_6\text{Hf}$ (607.19)	>250	27.5 (27.7)	3.0 (3.3)	31.5 (31.7)	-	29.3 (29.4)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7$ (1.9 + 0.88, 1 : 1)	30	$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)$ Light brown (75)	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{OS}_2\text{HfCl}$ (479.36)	220	35.0 (35.1)	3.2 (3.6)	13.3 (13.4)	7.3 (7.4)	37.2 (37.2)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7$ (1.9 + 2.6, 1 : 3)	40	$\text{Cp}_2\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)_3$ Off white (65)	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{S}_6\text{Hf}$ (739.27)	235	27.5 (27.6)	3.5 (3.5)	26.0 (26.0)	-	24.0 (24.1)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9$ (1.9 + 0.94, 1 : 1)	22	$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)$ Light brown (80)	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{OS}_2\text{HfCl}$ (493.38)	245	36.3 (36.5)	3.7 (3.9)	12.9 (13.0)	7.1 (7.2)	36.1 (36.1)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9$ (1.9 + 2.8, 1 : 3)	40	$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)_3$ Brown (62)	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3\text{S}_6\text{Hf}$ (691.35)	>250	34.6 (34.7)	4.5 (4.7)	27.7 (27.8)	-	25.8 (25.8)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11}$ (1.9 + 1.0, 1 : 1)	25	$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11})$ Light brown (75)	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{OS}_2\text{HfCl}$ (507.42)	205	37.8 (37.9)	4.1 (4.2)	12.5 (12.6)	6.8 (7.0)	35.1 (35.2)
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}_2 + \text{KS}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11}$ (1.9 + 3.0, 1 : 3)	38	$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11})_3$ Brown (70)	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_3\text{S}_6\text{Hf}$ (733.43)	215	37.6 (37.7)	5.0 (5.2)	26.1 (26.2)	-	24.2 (24.3)

region, which can be assigned^{10,11} to the charge-transfer band. The absence of a *d-d* transition rules out the presence of any unpaired electrons in the complexes.

Infrared spectra : The characteristic infrared spectral bands of the ligands and their complexes are given in Table 2. Absorption bands occurring at $\sim 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{C-H})$, $\sim 1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{C-C})$ and $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\delta(\text{C-H})$ in the complexes indicates the presence of a cyclopentadienyl ring. The appearance of only one band near 3000 cm^{-1} , indicates the pentahapto (η^5) nature of the cyclopentadienyl ring. However, in some areas of the spectra there is considerable overlap in the bands due to the cyclopentadienyl ring, alkyl groups of xanthate ligands. Our conclusions are based on the data reported for the $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{V}(\text{Xan})]^+$ complex ion¹².

metal xanthates which was further supported by Chatt *et al.*¹⁶.

In the complexes cited in this section, the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching bands appear at about $1060\text{--}1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The lowering of the frequency of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ band ($\sim 25\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the hafnium(IV) complexes as compared to free ligands, indicates the involvement of sulphur in bonding with the metal. The bands observed around $320\text{--}340\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the

Table 2. Characteristic IR spectral bands (cm^{-1}) for the complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{C-O-C})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{R-O})$	$\nu(\text{Hf-Cp})$	$\nu(\text{Hf-S})$
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)$	1235sb	1140sb	1035s	530m	400m	340w
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$	1240sb	1130sb	1030s	520m	380m	338w
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)$	1230sb	1150sb	1040s	535m	385m	330w
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)_3$	1240sb	1135sb	1038s	520m	390m	335w
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)$	1225sb	1160sb	1030s	530m	405m	340w
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)_3$	1220sb	1145sb	1040s	525m	400m	340w
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11})$	1230sb	1155sb	1030s	520m	390m	330w
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_5\text{H}_{11})_3$	1235sb	1150sb	1035s	520m	395m	320w

The main interest in the preparation of these complexes is the attachment of xanthate ligands. Xanthate ion can behave as a monodentate or bidentate ligand. However, assignment of the structure of metal xanthates from infrared data is not always reliable. All the xanthate ligands exhibit four characteristic bands around 1250 , 1100 , 1060 and 550 cm^{-1} which, according to Watt and McCormick¹³, are assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$, $\nu(\text{C-S})$, $\nu(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu(\text{R-O})$ vibrations, respectively. These bands are highly coupled and sensitive to environmental changes. A normal coordinate analysis of nickel(II) ethyl xanthate by Agarwala *et al.*¹⁴ indicates the 1250 cm^{-1} band has about 90% contribution from C-O-R stretch and 10% from $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretch. The band around 1100 cm^{-1} is mainly due to the contributions of C-O , R-O and $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching modes. The band around 1060 cm^{-1} has a single major contribution of 60% from the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretch. From a detailed investigation of the infrared spectra of various xanthato derivatives, Little *et al.*¹⁵ also assigned the band at $1060\text{--}1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and proposed the resonance forms (I) (a) and (b) as the most probable structure of

infrared spectra of the complexes may be assigned^{17,18} to $\nu(\text{Hf-S})$. The appearance of a single $\nu(\text{Hf-S})$ band indicates substantially equal interactions between the hafnium atom and the sulphur atoms in complexes. The $\nu(\text{Hf-Cl})$ frequency is observed at *ca.* $260\text{--}280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})$ complexes. The position of this band is shifted to a lower frequency. The shift in the position

has been attributed¹⁹ to bridging chlorine in a $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \text{Cl} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{M} \end{array}$ type arrangement.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra : The proton magnetic resonance spectra of some of these complexes have been recorded in deuterated chloroform and dimethylsulphoxide. Chemical shifts for protons in different chemical environments have been indicated in Table 3. The intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The resonance lines for the protons on the cyclopentadienyl ring always falls near δ 6.5–6.62 ppm. The appearance of a single, sharp signal for the protons of the cyclopentadienyl ring indicates the rapid rotation of the ring about the metal ring axis.

Table 3. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (δ , ppm) at 25 °C for the complexes

Complex	^1H NMR		^{13}C NMR			
	$-\text{C}_5\text{H}_5$	$-\text{CH}_2$	$-\text{CH}_3$	C_5H_5	$-\text{S}_2\text{CO}-$	Alkyl group
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)$	6.50s	3.0q	2.20t	117.5	140.2	17.8, 52.6
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$	6.55s	3.25q, 3.05q	2.25t, 1.90t	116.8	138.6, 142.4	15.6, 17.4, 50.8, 53.4
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)$	6.60s	3.30t, 3.10–2.90m	2.10t	117.0	142.5	15.8, 18.2, 50.3
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_3\text{H}_7)_3$	6.58s	3.35t, 3.25t, 3.10–2.80m	2.20t, 2.00t	117.2	140.2, 145.6	15.8, 16.2, 18.4, 19.3, 48.5, 51.0
$\text{Cp}_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)$	6.62s	3.28t, 3.15–2.80m	2.25t	116.9	140.8	14.6, 16.5, 25.6, 48.2
$\text{CpHf}(\text{S}_2\text{COC}_4\text{H}_9)_3$	6.50s	3.38t, 3.25t, 3.10–2.85m	2.28t, 1.95t	117.0	139.2, 143.8	14.5, 15.2, 16.8, 17.2, 25.2, 25.8, 48.0, 49.5

The two kinetic possibilities, viz. metal centered rearrangement is slow or fast, can be distinguished by the analysis of the proton magnetic resonance spectra. In the NMR spectra of tris(xanthato) derivatives, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Hf}(\text{Xan})_3$, two distinct signals for ethyl, propyl and butyl resonances are observed, which must result from non-equivalent environments.

The integrated proton ratios correspond to the formulae and attribute a trigonal-bipyramidal structure for the $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{Xan})$, and pentagonal-bipyramidal structures for the $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{Xan})_3$ derivatives. However, the structures of the complexes are bound to be slightly distorted due to the presence of a cyclopentadienyl ring in the molecule. On comparing the signals obtained for the ligands with that of the corresponding hafnium(IV) complexes, it has been found, that there is little variation in the chemical shifts of the protons on the OR groups. This variation may be attributed to the effect caused by the delocalisation of electrons between $\text{O}-\text{CS}_2$ of the ligand on coordination with hafnium.

^{13}C NMR spectra : The ^{13}C NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (Table 3). The salient features are :

(a) Due to cyclopentadienyl ring, the complexes show one resonance at *ca.* δ 117.0 (relative to TMS).

(b) In the ligands, the carbon signal of the $-\text{CS}_2$ group appears at δ 135.0 which shifts downfield in the complexes, confirming the bidentate nature of the CS_2 ligand group.

Thus the spectral data suggest that the xanthate ligands act as monobasic, bidentate chelating agents, coordinating through two sulphur atoms. For, $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ complexes, molecular weight measurements and IR

spectral data suggest molecular association. Therefore, chloro bridged structure (2) may be tentatively proposed.

The complexes of type $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3$ are found

(2)

Proposed structure of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ complexes.

to be monomer, and therefore, following structure (3) may be proposed having pentagonal-bipyramidal geometry.

(3)

Proposed structure of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Hf}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3]$ complexes.

The NMR data suggest that the three-xanthate groups are not equivalent. A non-equivalent environment is generated by the presence of the Cp ring, which may be present in the planar or axial position.

Experimental

All manipulations were performed under anhydrous conditions and under a dry O₂-free, N₂ atmosphere. THF (Merck) was dried by storage over sodium until it gave a blue colouration with benzophenone. Cp₂HfCl₂ was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. The potassium salts of alkyl xanthates were prepared by literature method⁹. The details of the analyses and physical measurements were the same as described earlier¹⁰.

Preparation of the complexes :

[Cp₂Hf(S₂COR)Cl] : To a solution of Cp₂HfCl₂ (5 mmol) in dry THF (*ca.* 35 mL) was added the appropriate xanthate (5 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for ~20–30 h. The solution was then filtered and its volume reduced to ~15 mL. To this was added petroleum ether (60–80°, ~20 mL) and the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The coloured crystals, so obtained, were filtered, washed thoroughly with ether and dried in an oven at 80 °C.

[CpHf(S₂COR)₃] : A mixture of Cp₂HfCl₂ (5 mmol) and appropriate xanthate (5 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (~40 mL) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for about 40 h. The resulting yellow or yellowish-brown precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with THF and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were recrystallised from benzene.

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